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Modern technologies of teaching English in distance learning conditions

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***Abstract.** Distance learning has become an integral part of the modern educational process, and it has become especially relevant during the COVID-19 pandemic. The study of foreign languages also did not remain aloof from these changes. Innovative technologies have opened up new opportunities for us to learn foreign languages effectively and interestingly. **The objective of the article** is to analyze modern technologies used for teaching English in distance learning conditions. **Methods.** The research uses a theoretical analysis of the literature on distance learning, digital learning and educational technologies, as well as generalization and systematization methods.*

***Results.** The author emphasizes the importance of digital tools, such as mobile applications, online platforms, artificial intelligence services, as well as the integration of virtual reality into the educational process. Special attention is paid to adaptive platforms that allow for individualization of training according to the student's level of knowledge, his needs and pace of work. It is noted that mobile applications such as*

Duolingo and Memrise promote interactivity through gamification, and video communication services such as Zoom or Microsoft Teams provide the possibility of live communication even at a distance. Artificial intelligence, particularly chatbots and voice recognition tools, is seen as an innovative tool for improving pronunciation, developing conversational skills and automating feedback.

The role of social networks and knowledge-sharing platforms such as HelloTalk or Tandem, which help students practice the language with native speakers in an informal atmosphere, is analyzed separately. The importance of podcasts, audiobooks, and interactive quizzes in developing listening skills and expanding vocabulary is also emphasized.

The advantages of distance learning with the help of technologies are determined: the availability of educational resources, the possibility of learning anywhere and anytime, the adaptability of programs and the motivational effect through game elements. Along with this, the article discusses the challenges associated with the use of technology, in particular the need for access to high-quality Internet and digital literacy of students and teachers.

Conclusions. *Modern technologies are a powerful tool in distance learning of the English language, able to increase the effectiveness of the educational process and make it more interesting and comfortable for users.*

Keywords: *distance education, digital technologies, educational technologies, interactivity, innovation.*

**Сучасні технології навчання англійській мові в умовах
дистанційного навчання**

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***Анотація.** Дистанційне навчання стало невід'ємною частиною сучасного освітнього процесу, а особливо актуальним воно стало під час пандемії COVID-19. Вивчення іноземних мов також не залишилося осторонь цих змін. Інноваційні технології відкрили перед нами нові можливості для ефективного та цікавого опанування іноземних мов. **Мета** статті полягає в аналізі сучасних технологій, які використовуються для навчання англійської мови в умовах дистанційного навчання. **Методи.** У дослідженні використовується теоретичний аналіз літератури з питань дистанційного навчання, цифрового навчання та освітніх технологій, а також методи узагальнення та систематизації.*

***Результати.** Автор акцентує увагу на значущості цифрових інструментів, таких як мобільні додатки, онлайн-платформи, сервіси штучного інтелекту, а також інтеграції віртуальної реальності у навчальний процес. Особлива увага приділяється адаптивним платформам, які дозволяють індивідуалізувати навчання відповідно до рівня знань студента, його потреб і темпу роботи. Зазначено, що мобільні додатки на кшталт Duolingo та Memrise сприяють інтерактивності завдяки гейміфікації, а сервіси для відеозв'язку, як Zoom або Microsoft Teams, забезпечують можливість живого спілкування навіть на відстані. Штучний інтелект, зокрема чат-боти та інструменти для розпізнавання голосу, розглядається як інноваційний інструмент для*

покращення вимови, розвитку розмовних навичок та автоматизації зворотного зв'язку.

Окремо аналізується роль соціальних мереж і платформ обміну знаннями, таких як HelloTalk або Tandem, які допомагають учням практикувати мову з носіями в неформальній атмосфері. Також підкреслюється важливість подкастів, аудіокниг та інтерактивних вікторин у розвитку навичок аудіювання та розширенні словникового запасу.

Визначено переваги дистанційного навчання за допомогою технологій: доступність навчальних ресурсів, можливість навчання будь-де і будь-коли, адаптивність програм і мотиваційний ефект через ігрові елементи. Разом із цим, у статті обговорюються виклики, пов'язані із застосуванням технологій, зокрема потреба в доступі до якісного інтернету та цифрової грамотності студентів і викладачів.

***Висновок.** Сучасні технології є потужним інструментом у дистанційному навчанні англійської мови, здатним підвищити ефективність навчального процесу та зробити його цікавішим і комфортнішим для користувачів.*

***Ключові слова:** дистанційна освіта, цифрові технології, освітні технології, інтерактивність, інновації.*

Introduction. Distance learning, as a form of education that uses information and communication technologies to transfer knowledge at a distance, has become an integral part of the modern educational process. The COVID-19 pandemic and the armed aggression of the Russian Federation against Ukraine only strengthened this trend, turning remote formats into the main ones for many educational institutions. In addition, the remote form of education has become widespread due to a number of other factors, in particular, the constant appearance of new technologies (fast Internet, video conferences, cloud services); the ability to study anytime, anywhere appeals to

today's students who value flexibility. Distance learning makes it possible to reduce the cost of education, which makes it more accessible to a wide range of students.

The development of distance education has opened up new opportunities for learning foreign languages, in particular English. Modern technologies have greatly facilitated this process by providing students with access to a variety of interactive learning materials and platforms. However, technologies are rapidly developing, changing, improving, new and more effective methods for learning a foreign language in the online format appear.

Analysis of recent research and publications. Distance learning has long been a key aspect of scientific research for many scientists, but since 2020, after the official introduction of distance learning in Ukraine, the attention of scientists to this issue has increased even more. In 2020, the number of studies devoted to distance learning increased, which is reflected in the review works of V. Kyurcheva [1], a study of the features of distance learning [2], specialized training [3], distance learning of foreign languages in non-formal education [4], etc. Thus, scientist N. Zaitseva investigated the advantages and disadvantages of innovations in the educational environment and the activities of teachers in the context of distance learning [5]. The researchers O. Khoroshaylo, S. Kochergina [6] and I. Kozibai [7]. The main aspects of the use of artificial intelligence technologies and their impact on improving the quality of foreign language teaching in higher education institutions became the subject of their research.

Highlighting previously unresolved parts of the overall problem. Despite a fairly significant amount of scientific research on distance learning and foreign language learning technologies in online education, this issue remains not fully explored, as new technologies are constantly emerging in response to modern challenges. The use of artificial intelligence technologies, in particular, when teaching a foreign language in a remote format, new forms of work and applications remain insufficiently researched, which determines the relevance of the chosen topic.

In the article, the author attempts to systematize the main innovative technologies of distance learning of a foreign language, to identify the advantages and disadvantages of their use. The feasibility of using various technologies is substantiated, taking into account the peculiarities of distance learning.

Formulation of the goals of the article. The purpose of our article is to comprehensively investigate and describe the role of modern technologies in the process of learning English in conditions where traditional face-to-face learning is partially or completely replaced by distance learning. To achieve the goal, the following tasks must be completed:

1. To analyze the current state of this issue: an overview of existing technological tools and platforms used for learning English online; comparing the effectiveness of various technologies and methods of learning in a distance format; identifying the advantages and disadvantages of using modern technologies in online English language learning.

2. To investigate the impact of technology on the learning process. How does technology affect students' motivation to learn English? How do technologies contribute to the development of various language skills (speaking, listening, reading, writing)? How does technology change the role of the teacher and the student in the learning process?

3. To study the most effective technologies for learning various aspects of the English language.

4. To determine the prospects of using new distance learning technologies in foreign language learning.

Research results. Distance learning is learning at a distance, in conditions of remoteness of the student and the teacher, which involves the use of electronic educational resources in an electronic educational environment, information and communication system of distance learning and technology of distance learning.

Distance learning technologies play an increasingly significant role in the modern educational process, especially in the study of foreign languages. Their use opens up new possibilities for effective and flexible learning for students and teachers. Let's consider and analyze the advantages of distance learning:

1. Flexibility of the learning process. First of all, it is an individual pace of work. Each student can study at his own pace, independent of other group members. Secondly, it is an opportunity to practice at any convenient time and in any place that has access to the Internet. In addition, this format of study makes it much easier to combine studies with work, family and other activities. Also, this distance learning format provides for greater flexibility and mobility not only of students, but also of teachers, in particular regarding the provision of consultations, distribution of time and workload.

2. Variety of interactive materials. Rich audio and video materials help develop listening and speaking skills. Various interactive exercises make the learning process more interesting and effective. Also, it is possible to create simulations of real situations, i.e. Creation of virtual environments where students can practice language in real situations.

3. Development of students' independence. Distance learning prepares students for constant self-improvement and mastering new knowledge. The student takes an active part in the educational process, developing self-organization and self-control skills.

4. Development of communication skills of students. The remote work format significantly expands the possible forms of work. Online platforms allow students to communicate with native speakers, which is important for developing speaking skills. Working together on projects develops teamwork and presentation skills.

5. Increasing the motivation of education seekers to learn a foreign language. Interactive elements and gamification make the learning process more interesting and exciting, which increases student motivation [8, p. 298].

Having many advantages in today's conditions, distance learning still has its disadvantages, which should not be ignored. In our opinion, taking into account the experience of working online with students, one of the biggest disadvantages of distance learning is the lack of opportunity for live communication with the teacher and other students. This makes it difficult to practice pronunciation, understand intonations and nuances of language. Unlike traditional education, where there is a clear schedule and control from the teacher, distance learning requires a high level of self-organization and motivation from the student, which is sometimes a problem, because not all students of higher education are able to self-organize and work effectively. Technical problems also play an important role. An unstable Internet connection, hardware or software problems can interfere with the educational process. There is no social interaction. Studying in an online format deprives students of the opportunity to communicate with fellow students in an informal setting, which can negatively affect their social adaptation and motivation. Also, some students may have difficulties with the perception and assimilation of the material. Some students learn better in traditional classes where they can ask questions and get immediate answers. In addition, distractions in the home environment can also make it difficult to concentrate on studies.

However, all the above-mentioned disadvantages can be overcome if you still want to qualitatively organize the online learning process in modern conditions. Use interactive platforms with video conferences, chats and forums. It allows students to communicate with the teacher and fellow students in real time. Provide regular feedback. The teacher should provide regular feedback on completed tasks so that the student can monitor his progress and receive the necessary help. If possible, combine

online classes with face-to-face meetings to balance the benefits of both formats. Technical support is also definitely important, because having quality technical support helps to solve problems related to hardware and software.

Despite the existing disadvantages, distance learning of foreign languages has a number of advantages, such as a flexible schedule, availability and variety of educational materials. In order to make online learning effective, it is necessary to take into account its features and use modern technologies and teaching methods.

Analyzing distance learning as a characteristic of today's educational process, one cannot overlook the role of the teacher in this process. The transition to distance learning presented new challenges to foreign language teachers and opened up many opportunities. The role of the teacher in this format of education has changed significantly. The functions of the teacher in the online education system have changed. The teacher is the designer of the learning environment. He creates interactive and interesting materials that engage students in learning, uses various tools and platforms to organize the learning process. The teacher is a motivator, because he supports a high level of student motivation, offers interesting tasks and projects, and creates an atmosphere of cooperation and mutual assistance. A teacher is a coach who helps his students develop independent work skills, sets goals for them and provides the necessary support to achieve them. Also, the teacher is a consultant in the educational process, as he provides individual consultations, answers questions and helps students overcome difficulties. Another unquestionably important role of the teacher is that of an evaluator, as the teacher develops a grading system that allows students to track their progress and provide feedback.

The work of a foreign language teacher in a distance format has its own specifics in contrast to the traditional form of education. The teacher must possess modern technologies and master new tools for organizing distance learning. Classes must be interesting and varied to keep students' attention, so it is important to create an

interactive mass environment. Modern technologies provide the teacher with a wide range of tools for creating interesting and effective classes. A teacher can create personalized learning plans for each student, taking into account their strengths and weaknesses [9].

Along with the opportunities, distance education also poses new challenges for teachers. One of the biggest challenges is the lack of opportunity for live communication with the teacher and classmates. This makes it difficult to practice pronunciation, understand intonations and nuances of language. There is no social interaction. Classroom learning involves social interaction that promotes motivation and engagement in learning. In an online environment, the lack of such opportunities can negatively affect the learning process. Technical problems are possible. An unstable Internet connection, hardware or software problems can prevent effective learning. In addition, distance learning requires a high level of self-organization and motivation from students. Without constant supervision from the teacher, it is easier to get distracted by other things. Another aspect that causes certain difficulties in distance learning is the assessment of students' knowledge. Fair assessment of students' knowledge in the online format is a difficult task. There is a risk of attrition and other types of academic fraud.

To solve such problematic issues, it is necessary to find ways to minimize them at the level of subsidization and involvement in grant support, optimization of educational platforms, infrastructure development, improvement of multilingualism and intercultural support. Using learning platforms that can be easily adapted to different levels of internet connectivity and technical capabilities. Lack of content or resources available in different languages can limit opportunities for students from different regions and ethnicities. The development and provision of educational resources in different languages, which takes into account the diversity of language groups in Ukraine, will allow students to immediately understand the material provided

for them to study. Engaging language experts to develop and check linguistic aspects of educational materials will significantly simplify the work of teachers and students at all levels of the educational process [7, p. 211].

The ability to interact and communicate effectively, taking into account both technical and social aspects, is key to the success of distance learning. Cooperation between teachers, development of quality teaching materials and mutual learning are important aspects of overcoming difficulties.

However, despite the challenges for both teachers and students, distance learning has become our reality. Learning foreign languages in the conditions of distance learning requires the use of innovative technologies that increase the efficiency and motivation of students [10].

One of the key technologies in distance learning is the use of specialized digital platforms. Digital platforms offer many tools and resources that make learning more effective, interactive and accessible. The following are the reasons for the effectiveness of such platforms:

- 1) Interactivity. Many platforms use games, exercises and other interactive elements that make learning more interesting and effective.
- 2) Personalization. Thanks to artificial intelligence algorithms, the platforms can adapt the educational process to the individual needs of each student.
- 3) Availability. The ability to study at any time and in any place, having only a device with access to the Internet.
- 4) Variety of materials. A large selection of educational materials, from text exercises to audio and video.
- 5) Feedback. Quick and detailed feedback on completed tasks [11, p. 149].

The following are among the most popular platforms for learning a foreign language: Duolingo, Memrise, Busuu (provide an interactive approach to learning vocabulary, grammar and pronunciation thanks to game mechanics); Coursera, edX,

Udemy (offer structured courses that include video lectures, assignments, and interactive exercises); Zoom, Microsoft Teams, Google Meet (useful for conducting group classes, conversation clubs and interacting with teachers in real time) [12, p. 192].

Artificial intelligence (AI) is a revolutionary tool in language learning. According to information from the UNESCO website, the use of AI technologies in education can improve human capabilities and facilitate effective human-machine collaboration. Many experts believe that AI has the potential to solve some of the biggest challenges in education today and to innovate learning and teaching practices.

First of all, AI can save time by suggesting a variety of materials and ideas provided the teacher creates a detailed request. Of course, not all of them are ready to use, but the system generates ideas for all kinds of language practice. Second, it can simplify assessment by creating tests and quizzes and providing easy, instant feedback for students at different levels. Ultimately, international students are given the opportunity to improve their writing skills outside of the classroom by interacting with the AI in English as if they were communicating with a native speaker via text messaging.

Artificial intelligence technologies can be used for learning in several ways. First, for planning lessons and adapting tasks. Artificial intelligence can help teachers develop effective lesson plans. By analyzing student progress, their learning styles, and individual needs, AI can recommend selected content and learning strategies for an optimal learning experience. You can also ask the system to make the tasks easier or harder depending on the level of the students. Secondly, for task generation and content creation. AI can create learning materials such as worksheets, quizzes, and reading texts based on specific language level and learning objectives. In addition, it is possible to generate exercises and questions, which facilitates the preparation of learning activities for teachers. The third way of using artificial intelligence is the

individualization of the learning process. AI systems can adapt to each student's individual needs and provide instruction based on their strengths and weaknesses. AI systems can also change the pace and focus according to student preferences, offering targeted exercises and feedback. AI can act as a source of information, giving both students and teachers access to language resources, dictionaries and translation tools. It also allows students to explore English on their own and helps teachers save time in providing references and explanations.

Despite all the benefits of using artificial intelligence in the classroom and for lesson preparation, there are significant concerns not only about the ethical aspects of content creation, but also about the reliability of information provided by artificial intelligence. It is important to find a balance between using AI tools and relying on other sources of information and the teacher's own knowledge.

There are several popular AI tools used in ESL education today, including Grammarly (text editing), Tutor AI (explanations), Pictory.AI (text-to-video tool + video editing, creating captions and subtitles), Craiyon (picture generation), and of course ChatGPT.

ChatGPT can be used to adapt text for different purposes and different levels; analysis of texts and creation of: a) vocabulary lists; b) questions; c) resume; d) other types of activities based on texts; giving examples and brainstorming ideas (for example, options for introductory and warm-up exercises); creation of instructions, ICQ and CCQ; checking written works and providing feedback on assignments; creation of tasks of the following types: choose the correct option, correct errors, fill in the blanks, open parentheses, paraphrase; creation of dialogues on certain topics, essays, generation of scenarios and stories; giving synonyms and opposites, etc.

When teaching English as a foreign language, it is important to remember to practice pronunciation and listening skills. ChatGPT cannot perform these functions, but Play.HT can. His voices can convey emotions and span over 130 languages,

allowing conversations to sound natural and human. It also offers over 800 male and female voices and voice cloning.

Twee is another AI tool that can help teachers. It helps you create questions, dialogues, stories, letters, articles, multiple choice questions, true/false statements in just a few seconds. Twee has no problem generating discussion questions or finding facts and quotes from famous people related to the topic you want.

In addition to 100% AI-powered tools, many well-known educational sites include some AI functionality (Canva, Google Classroom). However, if you want to try creating flash cards, slides and presentations more efficiently, try using sites with artificial intelligence - such as Tome.

Thus, by harnessing the power of AI, educators can provide more personalized and engaging language instruction, helping students achieve their language goals more effectively. And as technology continues to evolve, partnerships between AI and teachers promise to shape the future of English language teaching in unforeseen ways.

When introducing AI tools into the educational process, it is important to ensure their ethical use, which does not lead to replacement of teachers and does not violate grammatical rules. By staying abreast of the latest learning tools based on artificial intelligence and virtual reality, educators can prepare for the future use of AI in foreign language teaching and provide learners with an engaging and personalized learning experience. It is important to balance the use of artificial intelligence and the role of teachers in the educational process. Teachers play a key role in the development of students' critical thinking, creativity and social skills. They should use artificial intelligence technologies as a tool to improve the learning process while maintaining the importance of interpersonal interaction and cultural context [13, p. 322].

Among the technologies of distance learning of foreign languages, it is worth paying attention to the gamification of the educational process. Gamification is actively integrated into the learning process, because it makes language learning interesting and

motivating. Its main elements are: game tasks (for example, completing tasks in the format of quests); provision of virtual bonuses for educational achievements; the possibility of competition in groups or between students to develop a competitive spirit [14, p. 262]. For example, the platforms Duolingo and Lingualeo actively use these mechanics to keep students' attention. Gamification has become a real breakthrough in language learning. The Kahoot platform, for example, allows you to create quizzes, flashcards and interactive tasks that make learning fun and interesting.

Mobile apps are a versatile tool for on-the-go learning. Among them, the Quizlet service is popular - an interactive tool for learning new words and their long-term memorization, which is especially useful when learning foreign languages. The service provides for the creation and use of flash cards and educational games in various categories. Various modes such as Flashcards, Memorization, Writing, Spelling and Test allow you to learn vocabulary items in different ways, ensuring an efficient learning process. Quizlet also allows users to join groups, share sets, and create folders with their own files, making it a highly functional tool for effective foreign language learning.

When choosing a platform for learning a foreign language, it is necessary to take into account certain factors, namely the level of knowledge of students, the skills that need to be developed (reading, speaking, writing). For example, the Memrise platform focuses on memorizing words using mnemonic techniques and game elements. The Babbel platform pays special attention to conversational skills.

Virtual and augmented reality (VR/AR) technologies should not be neglected. VR/AR technologies allow you to immerse yourself in the language environment without the need for travel. For example:

1) Simulation of real communication: through applications such as Mondly VR, the user can "visit" virtual cafes, shops or meet other virtual interlocutors.

2) Game scenarios: interactive situations help practice vocabulary in context [15].

Social platforms such as YouTube, Instagram or TikTok are becoming a source of useful content created by native speakers. Online communities such as HelloTalk or Tandem allow exchange of knowledge between learners and native speakers using chat, video calling and translation features.

Conclusions. In today's world, technologies have become an integral part of the learning process, in particular, in the study of foreign languages. Innovative methods based on digital tools help make learning more accessible, effective and interesting. Modern technologies make learning accessible, because most tools work on smartphones and do not require significant costs; individual, as each student can create his own schedule and program; interactive, learning becomes dynamic and interesting; effective, because thanks to AI and large databases, technology allows you to quickly correct errors and achieve results. Modern technologies open new horizons for those who want to learn a foreign language. From mobile apps to virtual reality, everyone can find tools that fit their needs and learning style. The main thing is to be motivated, and modern technologies will help you achieve your goals.

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